

< **WAD** cher / >

State of the art of accessibility standards, evaluation tools, and technologies

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Keywords: web accessibility, accessibility assessment tools,
metrics for web accessibility

Web Accessibility Directive Decision Support Environment

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¹ <https://wadcher.eu/>

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Executive Summary

Disclaimer: This deliverable was finalised at the end of 2019. It reflects the state-of-the-art at that time. This field evolves continuously and may not reflect the state-of-the-art at the time the reader browses the document.

The WADcher project aims to provide an infrastructure to support monitoring of Web accessibility in Europe. This type of activity can be obtained only through the support of automatic validation tools. However, such tools must evolve in order to address the continuous technological evolution, and the corresponding change in accessibility guidelines.

This deliverable aims to provide an updated description of the state of art of the tools for automatic validation of accessibility guidelines. For this purpose, we have selected several web accessibility assessment tools according to several criteria (such as supporting at least the version 2.0 of WCAG and available in the English language). We also analyse some commercial accessibility services (including e.g. the Deque plugins for Chrome and Firefox, the Siteimprove Accessibility checker for Chrome, and the software developed by The Paciello Group). We compared them based on some critical features at the end of the section.

The deliverable also introduces metrics for accessibility evaluation, analyse relevant metrics for web accessibility, and report some research work that has been carried out on this topic, up to the most recent studies.

The analysis of the various accessibility validation tools has been carried out according to several dimensions: guidelines, languages supported, validation source, feedback provided, validation scope, whether DOM and/or CSS are checked, and plugin supported, and how the service is made available. For each tool we also provide relevant screenshots.

In the deliverable we also compare and discuss the most relevant tool features, such as validation scope, how they support customization of accessibility audits, overview of their validation results along with reports with details on the errors detected. The discussion includes remarks that can be useful for the further development of the WADcher set of tools based on the reviewed and collected information.

Disclaimer: Some of the descriptions contained in section 1 are based on the tool developers or manufacturers documentation and may not reflect the actual capabilities of the tools because not all of them have been fully reviewed by the consortium. The information in this document shall not be taken as any kind of endorsement from the consortium or from the European Commission.

This document has been reviewed incorporating responses to the information requested by the reviewers. This includes:

- Extending the analysis of the existing accessibility tools, which we have carried out by including the suggested tools (SiteImprove Accessibility (Stand-alone), deque WorldSpace Attest, deque WorldSpace Assure, deque WorldSpace Comply, TPG ARC Monitoring, TPG ARC Toolkit), see Section 1.3 Commercial Web Accessibility Services;
- Adding screenshots for all the analysed tools (see Section 1.2 Accessibility assessment tools and Section 1.3 Commercial Web Accessibility Services);

- Extending both the comparison and the comparative table considering the missing features (see Section 1.4 Comparison and Appendix: Summarizing table of the analysed tools);
- Looking at the results of the EIII project (see Section 1.2.7 EIII Tingtun);
- Updating the state of the art on accessibility metrics, which we have accrued out by considering the suggested recent work from China (see Section 2.2 Quantitative metrics for Web accessibility).
- Concluding requirements derived from the analysis. Section 3 has been revised also indicating how the requirements have been derived from the analysis carried out.
- Missing references have been included in section 4 (References).

1 Accessibility assessment tools

Disclaimer: Some of the descriptions contained in section 1 are based on the tool developers or manufacturers documentation and may not reflect the actual capabilities of the tools because not all of them have been fully reviewed by the consortium. The information in this document shall not be taken as any kind of endorsement from the consortium or from the European Commission.

1.1 Introduction

One of the many challenges people with various degrees of disabilities currently face is the difficulty in accessing products and services in an easy manner, thus being often excluded from benefiting from Web content and services in the same way people without disabilities do.

From this perspective, it is key to better support designers and developers in building and maintaining accessible and usable web services and apps. Although several guidelines, frameworks, and automatic and semi-automatic tools for accessibility compliance already exist, and already represent valuable tools to support developers and those expected to take decisions at governmental level, they present a number of limitations in the quality, completeness and accuracy of the provided support. In fact, automatic accessibility evaluation tools support developers and evaluators in also reducing the time and effort in conducting an accessibility evaluation, but they have weaknesses: tools cannot guarantee the automatic checking of the accessibility guidelines that require a human evaluation to assess if they are met or not, they tend to produce false positive and false negatives, and lastly the completeness of the results is not the same for all tools (Abascal, Arrue, & Valencia, 2019).

Thus, experts and policy makers need better solutions enabling fast processing of dynamic and large volumes of web pages/content and data, detecting accessibility hurdles and assisting them in repairing them. For this purpose, one of the main goals of the WADcher project is to research and develop an innovative decision-support environment for large scale hybrid (supporting automatic and manual assessment) web accessibility assessment services, able to enhance and then integrate existing web accessibility solutions, and also make them customizable to the needs of different stakeholders in various EU member states. However, in order to achieve such ambitious innovation and develop the envisioned solution, it is important to perform a thorough analysis of the state of the art of existing tools, technologies and services that currently support assessing the accessibility of websites.

Previous work (Schiavone and Paternò, 2015) proposed a categorization of tools for the automatic evaluation of multiple guideline sets, based on the fact that the description of the guidelines was expressed through an external language or an internally defined one, and also distinguishing between a "deterministic" and a "probabilistic" approach to the validation. Another possible way to classify accessibility evaluation tools is to consider their following features: if they are free or commercial, their type of platform (standalone application, browser extension, online service), their evaluation scope, if they support the repairing in addition to the evaluation, how accessibility issues are reported, the guidelines used. We referred to those classifications criteria in our analysis.

In this analysis, among the many tools available to developers for assessing the accessibility of websites, we have selected many automatic accessibility validators, considering also some well-known commercial solutions for web accessibility services. As a first source of information, we have consulted the list of tools provided by the W3C Consortium², focusing first on those that consider the WCAG 2.1 and WCAG 2.0 guidelines and that support at least the English language (for this reason we have excluded tools such as Hera FFX³ and Vamolà⁴). Then we looked at those supporting analysis of at least both (X)HTML and CSS, and covered most guidelines (thus we discarded those considering for example only colours) and that are freely accessible, available either online or as desktop applications. On the commercial side, we have looked at the tools offered by Imergo, Deque Systems⁵, Siteimprove⁶, Make Sense⁷ and The Paciello Group⁸ (which also offers an educational e-learning program, the TPG Tutor). The following analysis also considers Deque plugins for Chrome and Firefox – aXe plugins – and the Siteimprove Accessibility checker for Chrome.

In addition to supporting WCAG guidelines, some of the considered tools allow web designers and developers to check the accessibility against additional national guidelines: MAUVE⁹, for example, enables the user to select the Stanca Act for the validation; Asqatasun¹⁰ the French guidelines (RGAA¹¹); AChecker¹² the guidelines of the German government (BITV); Siteimprove extends the available guidelines to the JIS (Japanese Industry Standard).

When selecting the tools, we also took into account some technical issues: firstly, the audit depth of these tools, that is their validation scope (if they validate single web pages and/or entire websites, and also password protected pages); secondly, the validation source, that is the way how developers can start the validation of the web page (copied URL, file upload, directly entered code). In the end, we have checked if they allow the customization of accessibility audits, for example if the developer can specify the guidelines or their priority level for the validation.

Lastly, we focused on the presentation of test results provided. First, we identified the report type: if it is mainly code-oriented, statistical, or graphical (or a mix of these features). Then, we looked at the differentiation they make between different types of problems: errors, warnings, potential problems and information, that usually require additional manual check. In the end, we observed both the summarizing overview and the full report of the validation that they provide, and the kind of filtering that it is possible to apply to the results in order to get specific information.

Below is a detailed analysis of each tool, enriched with screenshots of the main views (the evaluation form with customization options and the evaluation report provided). For the

² <https://www.w3.org/WAI/ER/tools/>

³ <http://www.sidar.org/recur/aplica/heraffx.php>

⁴ http://www.validatore.it/vamola_validator/checker/index.php

⁵ <https://www.deque.com/products/>

⁶ <https://accessibility.siteimprove.com/>

⁷ <http://mk-sense.com/>

⁸ <https://www.paciellogroup.com/>

⁹ <http://mauve.isti.cnr.it/>

¹⁰ <http://asqatasun.org/>

¹¹ <http://references.modernisation.gouv.fr/rgaa-accessibilite/>

¹² <http://achecker.ca/>

commercial tools and services, we report a detailed description only for the free browser extensions offered by Deque and Siteimprove (A-ToGo, which is the Make Sense browser extension for Chrome, is not free), while for the other tools we based our report on the information provided by their websites, free trials and videos, and the information given in the W3C tools list.

At the time of writing this document, the accessibility evaluation of native mobile applications is either mostly a manual process depending on the platform used or focused on the verification within the different Integrated Development Environments of the use by the author of the corresponding accessibility APIs (for instance, iOS or android). Authoring tools are outside the scope of the project. As you can see in the following, some tools provide emulation of mobile browsers, allowing a partial evaluation of hybrid mobile applications, which are running in a browser window.

1.2 Accessibility assessment tools

1.2.1 AChecker

Released in 2008 by The Inclusive Design Research Centre (IDRC) at OCAD University (Canada), it checks single HTML pages for conformance with accessibility standards to ensure the content can be accessed by everyone.

Release date	2008
Languages	English, German, Italian
Guidelines	WCAG 1.0, WCAG 2.0, Stanca Act, Section 508, BITV
License	Open source, Free Software
Type of service	Online
Browser extension	-
Language framework	PHP + MySql
Audit depth	Single web pages, restricted or password protected pages
Validation source	Copied URL, File Upload and Pasted HTML
Customization of accessibility audits	Allows users to create their own guidelines, and author their own accessibility checks. It's possible to choose the guidelines that you want to use and the priority level for WCAG 1.0, WCAG 2.0 and BITV 1.0 It's also possible to enable HTML or CSS validation
PRESENTATION OF TEST RESULTS	
Report type	Code-oriented, statistical
Granularity level of results interpretation	Results are divided into: known problems, likely problems and potential problems.
Summarizing overview	The results are divided into known problems, likely problems and potential problems. If HTML or CSS

	validation is enabled, it's possible to see their results. The validation is based on the guidelines chosen.
Full report	Errors and warnings are provided in the line number where they occur. The tool provides a first suggestion to repair the errors/warnings but it's possible to see a full explanation with some example.
Not provided	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Visualization of fail/warnings on rendered web page - Pinpointing of fail/warning in DOM

Figure 1 – AChecker validation form

Figure 2 – AChecker full report

1.2.2 Asqatasun

Released in 2016, developed by asqatasun.org (France), it also addresses SEO concerns and it is extensible to other domains. For the validation demonstration the demo version (online at <https://app.asqatasun.org/login.html>) was used.

Release date	2016
---------------------	------

Languages	English, French and Spanish
Guidelines	WCAG 2.0, RGAA
License	Free software, open source
Type of service	Online
Browser extension	-
Language framework	-
Audit depth	Single pages, groups of web pages or web sites, restricted or password protected web pages
Validation source	Copied URL, HTML file upload, Scenario upload
Customization of accessibility audits	It's possible to choose the priority level for RGAA (A, AA, AAA)
PRESENTATION OF TEST RESULTS	
Report type	Code oriented, statistical
Granularity level of results interpretation	Results are divided into: passed, failed, pre-qualified, not applicable and not tested.
Summarizing overview	It's possible to see the source code. The errors/warnings are divided into five categories based on the guideline chosen before and its level.
Full report	Errors and warnings are provided in the line number where they occur. The errors are provided in the form of a question and provide you a first suggestion to repair them and an explanation. The validation is divided in eleven categories: images, frames, multimedia, tables, links, scripts, mandatory elements, information structure, presentation of information, forms and consultation. So the user can filter reports by Web content type.
Not provided	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Visualization of fail/warnings on rendered web page - Pinpointing of fail/warning in DOM

Audit of pages

The fields with an asterisk (*) are required.

Pages to check

* URL 1 [Add Pages](#)
Fill-in at least one page address.

Details

Level

Level

HTML markers

Data table marker
Correspond to the attribute "id", "class" or "role" of the data tables. Multiple elements can be filled-in separated by a ;

Presentation table marker
Correspond to the attribute "id", "class" or "role" of the presentation tables. Multiple elements can be filled-in separated by a ;

Complex table marker
Correspond to the attribute "id", "class" or "role" of the the complex table. Multiple elements can be filled-in separated by a ;

Decorative Image marker
Correspond to the attribute "id", "class" or "role" of the decorative images. Multiple elements can be filled-in separated by a ;

Informative Image marker
Correspond to the attribute "id", "class" or "role" of the informative images. Multiple elements can be filled-in separated by a ;

Resolution

Screen width
Screen width of the screen in pixels

Screen height
Screen height of the screen in pixels

Colour contrast

The page provides a mechanism that enables to improve contrasts (style switcher)

[Launch the audit](#)

Figure 3 – Asqatasun validation form

Figure 4 – Asqatasun validation overview

Figure 5 – Asqatasun validation full report

1.2.3 Cyntia Says

Released in 2015, developed by Cryptzone (USA), it helps users identify errors in their Web content related to Section 508 standards and/or the WCAG guidelines for Web accessibility. It provides feedback in a reporting format that is clear and easy to understand.

Release date	2015
Languages	English
Guidelines	WCAG 2.0, Section 508
License	Freemium
Type of service	Online
Browser extension	Chrome, FireFox
Language framework	-
Audit depth	Single web pages
Validation source	Copied URL
Customization of accessibility audits	It's possible to choose the guidelines and the priority level for WCAG 2.0
PRESENTATION OF TEST RESULTS	
Report type	Code oriented, statistical
Granularity level of results interpretation	Results are divided into: failed, warning, passed, visual and N/A
Summarizing overview	It's not possible to see the source code and the results are divided into failed, warning, passed, visual and N/A.
Full report	Errors and warnings are provided in the line number where they occur. The tool provides you a first suggestion to repair them and an explanation of the guideline.
Not provided	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Visualization of fail/warnings on rendered web page - Pinpointing of fail/warning in DOM

TEST YOUR SITE NOW

Email Address*

Web Page URL*

Compliance mode*

I agree to the [Terms & Conditions](#). You must agree to the [Terms & Conditions](#).

TEST YOUR SITE

Figure 6 – Cyntia Says validation form

<http://wadcher.eu> - WCAG 2.0 AA

Scan Results:

[View a printable screen-reader-friendly version in a new window](#)

Scan completed: 24/09/2019 05:42:10

Group	All issues
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Compliance Level A	58
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Compliance Level AA	18
<p>The next level of conformance to the WCAG 2.0 guidelines. To declare AA conformance with WCAG 2.0 all criteria in Level A must also be met.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Criterion 1.4.3 [Contrast (Minimum)] <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Criterion 1.4.4 [Resize text] <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Criterion 1.4.5 [Images of Text] <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Criterion 2.4.6 [Headings and Labels] <p>The intent of this Success Criterion is to help users understand what information is contained in Web pages and how that information is organized. When headings are clear and deive, users can find the information they seek more easily, and they can understand the relationships between different parts of the content more easily. Deive labels help users identify specific components within the content.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> G130 Provide descriptive headings <p>The objective of this technique is to make section headings within Web content deive. Deive headings and titles (see G88: Providing deive titles for Web pages) work together to give users an overview of the content and its organization. Deive headings identify sections of the content in relation both to the Web page as a whole and to other sections of the same Web page.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Verify header identifies its section of content <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> https://wadcher.eu/ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Line 143, column 3, h1 element • Line 191, column 51, h2 element • Line 194, column 65, h2 element <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Criterion 2.4.7 [Focus Visible] <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Criterion 3.1.2 [Language of Parts] <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Criterion 3.2.3 [Consistent Navigation] <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Criterion 3.2.4 [Consistent Identification] <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Criterion 3.3.3 [Error Suggestion] <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Criterion 3.3.4 [Error Prevention (Legal, Financial, Data)] <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Criterion 1.2.4 [Captions (Live)] <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Criterion 1.2.5 [Audio Description] <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Criterion 2.4.5 [Multiple Ways] 	
Total	76

Figure 7 – Cyntia Says full report

1.2.4 MAUVE

First version released in 2012 by the Human Interfaces in Information Systems Laboratory - ISTI-CNR (Italy), it checks both HTML and CSS and, through some browsers' plugins (Chrome and Firefox), it can validate dynamic sites. Accessibility guidelines can be defined and updated through an XML-based definition language, without requiring changes in the tool implementation.

Release date	2012
Languages	English
Guidelines	WCAG 2.1, WCAG 2.0, Stanca Act, Visually Impaired
License	Free Software
Type of service	Online
Browser extension	Chrome, FireFox
Language framework	JAVA
Audit depth	Single web pages
Validation source	Copied URL, File Upload and Paste HTML
Customization of accessibility audits	It's possible to choose the guidelines and the priority level for WCAG 2.0 It can validate also dynamic sites

PRESENTATION OF TEST RESULTS	
Report type	Code-oriented, statistical
Granularity level of results interpretation	Results are divided into errors and warnings
Summarizing overview	The results are divided into errors and warnings and they are based on the guideline chosen at the beginning of the validation
Full report	Errors and warnings are provided in the line number where they occur. It's possible to see the source code. The tool provides users with a first suggestion to repair the errors/warnings but it's possible to see a full explanation with some example.
Not provided	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Visualization of fail/warnings on rendered web page - Pinpointing of fail/warning in DOM

MAUVE

Validation Environment About Bug report

Your URL Your File Your Code

Enter the URL you would like to check Validate

YOUR CONTENT WILL BE VALIDATED AGAINST:

Level of conformance

WCAG 2.1 WCAG 2.0 AA

Select a device (User Agent)

PC Desktop

Accessibility guidelines

- WCAG 2.1 (ENG)
- WCAG 2.0 (ENG)
- Stanca Act (ENG)
- Stanca Act (ITA)
- Visually Impaired (ENG)

This is MAUVE validator v 2.2

M.A.U.V.E. validator is a project of HIIS Lab at ISTI - CNR, currently maintained by Fabio Paternò, Antonio Giovanni Schiavone, Marco Manca, Francesca Pulina and Giovanna Broccia.

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Figure 8 – MAUVE validation form

Figure 9 – MAUVE evaluation overview

Figure 10 – MAUVE full report for end users

Figure 11 – MAUVE full report for web developers

1.2.5 TAW Web

Taw Web is an online tool developed by Fundación CTIC (Spain) introduced more than 15 years ago, being the reference tool in Spanish-speaking countries. It is part of a suite of tools named Tawdis. TAW Web validates web pages and websites against the WCAG 2.0 guidelines; the latest version has been improved so as to validate also the accessibility of the code produced by JavaScript. The problems checked can be divided into “Automatic” (problems that the tool detects by itself, and which must be solved) and “Manual” (possible problems that the evaluator should confirm or discard).

Release date	?
Languages	English, Spanish, Portuguese
Guidelines	WCAG 2.0, WCAG 2.1
License	Free software
Type of service	Online
Browser extension	-
Language framework	?
Audit depth	Single web pages, web sites
Validation source	Copied URL
Customization of accessibility audits	The user can choose the analysis level (A, AA, or AAA) and the supported technologies (HTML, CSS, JS; HTML and CSS are selected by default) against which it analyses the web page.
PRESENTATION OF TEST RESULTS	

Report type	Code oriented, statistical
Granularity level of results interpretation	Identified problems are classified into: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Problems (Corrections are needed) • Warnings (A human review is necessary) • Not reviewed (Fully manual review)
Summarizing overview	It reports the total number of Problems, Warnings and Not reviewed. For each of these three categories, the total number of success criteria where the problems have been found is indicated; then, the number of problems found for each accessibility principle is indicated.
Full report	The full report is sent via email to the address provided by the user. It consists of four tables, each one representing an accessibility principle. In each table, problems are presented ordered by guideline and success criteria (no filtering is provided). For each problem the following aspects are indicated: typology (images, presentation, structure and semantics, ...), a short description of the problem, links to the related W3C Techniques, type of problem (Fail, Unknown, Not checked), line number(s) where it occurred.
Not provided	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Visualization of fail/warnings on rendered web page - Pinpointing of fail/warnings in the source code - Pinpointing of fail/warning in DOM - Filtering of the overview and full report results

Figure 12 – TAW web validation form

Figure 13 – TAW Web evaluation overview

1.2.6 The A11Y Machine

Released in 2017 by Liip (Switzerland), it is an automated accessibility testing tool which crawls and tests pages of any web application to produce detailed reports. This software is backed by Liip, a company that offers a wide range of digital services using methods from Design Thinking and User-Centred Design.

Release date	23/08/2017 (version: 0.9.3)
Languages	English
Guidelines	WCAG 2.0, WCAG 1.0, Section 508, W3C HTML5 Recommendation
License	Free software, open source
Type of service	Npm installation (details: https://github.com/liip/TheA11yMachine)
Browser extension	-
Language framework	Node.js
Audit depth	Single web pages, groups of web pages or web sites, restricted or password-protected web pages.
Validation source	Copied URL, or list of URLs.
Customization of accessibility audits	The user can choose the standard against which it tests the web pages. Possible options are: 'WCAG2A', 'WCAG2AA' (default), 'WCAG2AAA', 'Section508', 'HTML'. Standards cannot be combined each other, except HTML5 Recommendation, which can be combined with any other. The user can also decide to filter or exclude results by comma-separated WCAG codes (e.g. 'H25, H91, G18').
PRESENTATION OF TEST RESULTS	
Report type	The report is code-oriented and statistical. 3 reports are provided: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Index of the Accessibility reports • Accessibility report of a specific URL (selected from the list of reports) • The dashboard of all reports

Granularity level of results interpretation	<p>Results are divided into:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Notice • Warning • Error
Summarizing overview	<p>The overview is a list of the analysed web pages, which can be sorted by errors/warnings/notices. A summarizing pie chart shows the percentage of all notices (in blue colour), warnings (orange) and errors (red).</p> <p>For each web page the following information is provided: a small pie chart, the URL of the web page, all WCAG notes related to the identified problems (they are links to the W3C Understanding page).</p>
Full report	<p>For each analysed web page, a full report is provided. Percentages of notices, warnings and errors are showed again through a pie chart.</p> <p>This report can be filtered by status of issues, and can be sorted by document order or by category (WCAG – HTML5 Recommendations).</p> <p>Every issue is accompanied by an explanation of the problem, the WCAG note code (e.g. H91), the violated WCAG principle-guideline-success criterion, the DOM and HTML elements where the problem has been found. The code line number is not provided.</p> <p>Lastly, the dashboard of all reports provides a scatterplot showing the notices/errors/warnings trend over time. Date and some statistics of each report are provided.</p>
Not provided	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Visualization of fail/warnings on rendered web page - Filtering of the full report by <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Web content type

Accessibility report

Generated at Fri Feb 05 2016 13:58:45 GMT+0100 (CET).

Sort by: **errors** warnings notices

[See all notes](#)

<https://www.liip.ch/en/what>

Note codes: [H25](#), [H77](#), [H78](#), [H79](#), [H80](#), [H81](#), G...

<https://www.liip.ch/en/contact>

Note codes: [H25](#), [H77](#), [H78](#), [H79](#), [H80](#), [H81](#), G...

<https://www.liip.ch/en>

Note codes: [H25](#), [H77](#), [H78](#), [H79](#), [H80](#), [H81](#), G...

Figure 14 – The A11y Machine validation overview

Accessibility report for “<https://www.liip.ch/en/what>”

Generated at Fri Feb 05 2016 13:59:42 GMT+0100 (CET).

[Back to report listing](#)

Filter by: **errors** warnings notices

Sort by: document order category

WC Error: Anchor element found with a valid href attribute, but no link content has been supplied.

Note codes: [H91](#) #WCAG2AA.Principle4.Guideline4.1.4.1.2.H91.A.NoContent

```
#header > div:nth-child(2) > div > div:nth-child(1) > div > a
</ > <a href="/en" class="logo-with-claim-logo"></a>
```

HTML Error: Bad value “schema.dc” for attribute “rel” on element “link”: The string “schema.dc” is not a registered keyword.

```
</ > <link rel="schema.dc" href="http://purl.org/metadata/dublin_core_elements"/>
```

Figure 15 – The A11y Machine full report

Figure 16 – The A11y Machine Dashboard

1.2.7 EIII Tingtun

The European Internet Inclusion Initiative Checker (EIII Checker) has been designed and implemented as part of the EIII project supported by the European Commission¹³. This was a Coordination and Support Action running from October 2013 until September 2015. The only public result that is still available of that project is the Tingtun checker¹⁴. This tool provides a Page Checker and a PDF Checker. The Page Checker analyses the page content against tests derived from the WCAG 2.0 success criteria, reporting results that are classified into pass, fail or to be verified. The tests are carried out on the page after JavaScript and CSS have been applied. The PDF Checker, based on the WCAG 2.0 PDF Techniques, analyses the PDF document – which can be uploaded or specified as a URL – detecting the potential barriers. More details in the table below.

Release date	01/01/2013
Languages	English, Norwegian
Guidelines	WCAG 2.0
License	Open source
Type of service	Online
Browser extension	-
Language framework	?

¹³ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/609667/it>

¹⁴ <http://checkers.eiii.eu/>

Audit depth	Single web pages
Validation source	Page Checker: copied URL PDF Checker: URI or File Upload
Customization of accessibility audits	Not provided.
PRESENTATION OF TEST RESULTS	
Report type	Code-oriented, statistical.
Granularity level of results interpretation	Results (<i>Applied Test</i>) are divided into: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fail • Verify • Pass
Summarizing overview	<p>The overview first provides the total number of Applied Test, and among them the number of fail, verify and pass. Then a Score, which is a number between 0 and 100, where 100 is the best. Finally, a sharable link to the result details.</p> <p>It is not possible to filter the number of Applied Tests by priority level of guidelines, nor by Web content types.</p>
Full report	<p>The full report consists of a list of the guidelines that regard the <i>Applied tests</i>, and can be filtered by the status of the issue encountered: fail, verify and pass. The guidelines reported are ordered by WCAG principle, guideline and success criterion (not by priority level).</p> <p>For each guideline reported, the number of fail/verify/pass regarding it is indicated. Then, for each fail, the code extract where the error occurs is reported and highlighted (the line number is not provided).</p> <p>A “Test info” section then provides a description of the concerned principle, guideline and success criterion, with links to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - W3C Understanding - W3C Techniques
Not provided	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Visualization of fail/warnings on rendered web page - Pinpointing of fail/warning in DOM - Filtering of the full report by <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Priority level ○ Web content types

eAccessibility / Page Checker

Check the Accessibility of a Web Page

Web page address:

Figure 17 – Tingtun validation form

Result Details

Applied Tests

Show Fail Verify Pass

Applied Tests	Results
Use alt on img elements [1.1.1]	✓6, ✗1
Use of Color [1.4.1]	✓86
Provide descriptive titles for web pages [2.4.2]	✓1
Provide links to navigate to related Web pages [2.4.5]	✓1
Provide descriptive headings [2.4.6]	✓9
Primary language of page [3.1.1]	✓1
Submit forms without submit buttons [3.2.2]	✗1
Provide a submit button to initiate a change of context [3.2.2]	✓1
Label groups of form elements [3.3.2]	✓1
Define ids for elements [4.1.1]	✓116, ✗1
Accessible name for image links [4.1.2]	✓3
Use HTML form controls and links [4.1.2]	✓140
Provide role name for div/span with event handler [4.1.2]	✓74

Test Detail: Use alt on img elements (H37)
(Test for Success Criterion 1.1.1: Non-text Content)

Results **Test info**

✗ **img has no alt (1 occurrence)**
Images have not alt attribute

- Path: <not available>

Heading: Code
Code extract:

```

```

✓ **img has alt (6 occurrences)**
Images have alt attribute

Figure 18 – Tingtun full report

1.2.8 Total Validator

Total Validator is developed in UK and it supports validation of single web page (Basic version) and websites (Pro version) against HTML5 recommendations, WCAG guidelines and Section 508 standard, CSS. It also provides a spell check and a broken links checker. Released in the 2005, it has been recently updated with new overall issues that apply across all pages tested, simplified selection of HTML5, more WCAG 2.0.

Release date	2005 (latest version: 14.1.1, released on 18/08/2019)
Languages	English (the spell checker detects the following languages: English, French, Italian, Spanish and German)
Guidelines	WCAG 2.0, WCAG 1.0, Section 508
License	Freemium (Basic version: free, Pro version: commercial)
Type of service	Desktop application
Browser extension	Chrome, Firefox
Language framework	?
BASIC VERSION	

Audit depth	Single web pages, restricted or password-protected web pages (the input field where to specify the n° of web pages to check is disabled in this version).
Validation source	Copied URL
Customization of accessibility audits	The user can choose: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To use ARIA rules for validation - The guidelines against which to validate (for WCAG also the analysis level) - To enable/disable the check for broken links, the spell check, and the DOM validation - To filter results by selecting what to not report: extra info, warnings, probable errors (they are all reported by default)
PRESENTATION OF TEST RESULTS	
Report type	Code oriented. The report format is an HTML5 file.
Granularity level of results interpretation	Results are classified into: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Errors • Warnings
Summarizing overview	It provides the total number of errors and warnings. The latter cannot be filtered by the level of guidelines, but both errors and warnings are subdivided into categories (spell check, link, parsing, HTML, WCAG 2.0, ...) and grouped according to same problems. Each problem has a code with a link to their Reference section, explaining details of the issue checked.
Full report	The full report consists of the HTML code of the web page analysed, with errors and warnings highlighted (errors in red, warnings in yellow). The user can choose the “Short report” option, which hides the non-problematic code lines. The issue details can be displayed by hovering on the highlighted lines (default), but they can also be all shown/hidden; they contains a brief explanation of the problems, and tips to fix them (sometimes links to W3C Techniques are also provided).
Not provided	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CSS validation (in Basic version) - Visualization of fail/warnings on rendered web page - Filtering of the full report

Figure 19 – Total Validator free validation form

1.2.9 WaaT

The Web Application Assessment Tool (WaaT, Oikonomou et al., 2011), developed by CERTH/ITI (Greece), is a tool available in two versions: Web and Standalone. Its Core Web Applications Assessment Module has all components needed to evaluate every aspect of a web site and web application during the analysis: the Web crawler, the HTML and CSS parsers, the W3C markup and CSS validators, the Web accessibility evaluator.

Source: <http://www.accessible-eu.org/index.php/waat.html>

Video presentation: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fhKkNo_jyTM

Release date	September 2011 (latest release: August 2012)
Languages	English
Guidelines	WCAG 2.0, WCAG 1.0, WAI-ARIA 1.0
License	Free software, Open source
Type of service	Online, desktop stand-alone application
Browser extension	-
Language framework	Java
Audit depth	Single web pages, groups of web pages or web sites (it's possible to specify the n° of pages to check in the site)
Validation source	Copied URL, pasted source code
Customization of accessibility audits	The user can choose “approaches” (assessment criteria) manually. All principles, guidelines and success criteria are selected by default. Users can also select specific impairments, disabilities and functional limitations, and the tool returns the related success criteria needed to satisfy the related accessibility requirements. Moreover,

	the selection of Personas (reflecting an impairment or more impairments at a time) is supported.
Possible to create own test rules?	Yes – By extending the ontologies where the description of the accessibility standards, disabilities, personas, mappings between accessibility guidelines-disabilities/personas, etc. is being stored in a semantic manner.
PRESENTATION OF TEST RESULTS	
Report type	Code oriented. The report is available in PDF and EARL format. A PDF version of the EARL-based report as well as a report using the HTTP Vocabulary in RDF are also available.
Granularity level of results interpretation	Results are divided into: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Errors • Warnings (need further investigation by the user: s/he can mark a warning as an error or ignore it)
Summarizing overview	<p>A first reduced report is provided, automatically divided into 3 sections: level A, level AA, level AAA.</p> <p>The report consists of a list of the violated guidelines ordered by principle, with associated total number of errors/warnings.</p> <p>An accessibility score (%) of the examined page(s) is provided (whereas 100% corresponds to fully accessible according to the conducted tests). This is actually a normalized version of the Web Accessibility Barrier (WAB) metric (Parmanto and Zeng, 2005).</p>
Full report	<p>The specific success criterion is visible after a click on the guideline, or in the fully extended report. Here are also provided:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Line number and code snippet where the problem occurred • Tips to correct the error • Indication of the W3C Techniques related to the problem at issue
Not provided	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Visualization of fail/warnings on rendered web page - Pinpointing errors/warnings in DOM

Figure 20 – WaaT validation form

Principle 1: Perceivable - Information and user interface components must be presentable to users in ways they can perceive

- Guideline 1.1 Text Alternatives: Provide text alternatives for any non-text content so that it can be changed into other forms people need, such as large print, b
- Guideline 1.2 Time-based Media: Provide alternatives for time-based media (0 Error(s), 0 Warning(s))
- Guideline 1.3 Adaptable: Create content that can be presented in different ways (for example simpler layout) without losing information or structure (3 Error(s), 0 Warning(s))
- Guideline 1.4 Distinguishable: Make it easier for users to see and hear content including separating foreground from background (0 Error(s), 0 Warning(s))

Principle 2: Operable - User interface components and navigation must be operable

- Guideline 2.1 Keyboard Accessible: Make all functionality available from a keyboard (6 Error(s), 0 Warning(s))
- Guideline 2.2 Enough Time: Provide users enough time to read and use content (0 Error(s), 0 Warning(s))
- Guideline 2.3 Seizures: Do not design content in a way that is known to cause seizures (0 Error(s), 0 Warning(s))
- Guideline 2.4 Navigable: Provide ways to help users navigate, find content, and determine where they are (2 Error(s), 87 Warning(s))

Principle 3: Understandable - Information and the operation of user interface must be understandable

- Guideline 3.1 Readable: Make text content readable and understandable (0 Error(s), 1 Warning(s))
- Guideline 3.2 Predictable: Make Web pages appear and operate in predictable ways (1 Error(s), 0 Warning(s))
- Guideline 3.3 Input Assistance: Help users avoid and correct mistakes (3 Error(s), 3 Warning(s))

Principle 4: Robust - Content must be robust enough that it can be interpreted reliably by a wide variety of user agents, including assistive technologies

- Guideline 4.1 Compatible: Maximize compatibility with current and future user agents, including assistive technologies (25 Error(s), 53 Warning(s))

Accessibility score of the examined page(s) : 71.50 %

Figure 21 – WaaT full report

1.2.10 WAVE

Released in 2014 and developed by WebAIM (USA), it is a suite of tools for facilitating web accessibility evaluation by providing a visual representation of accessibility issues within the page. There is an online service and an online and installable API engine. Browser plugin: Firefox and Chrome.

Release date	2014
Languages	English

Guidelines	WCAG 2.0, Stanca Act
License	Free Software
Type of service	Online
Browser extension	Chrome, FireFox
Language framework	-
Audit depth	Single web pages, restricted or password protected web pages
Validation source	Copied URL
Customization of accessibility audits	It's not possible to choose the guidelines and the priority level
PRESENTATION OF TEST RESULTS	
Report type	Statistical
Granularity level of results interpretation	Results are divided into: errors, alerts, features, structural elements, HTML5 and ARIA and contrast errors
Summarizing overview	It's not possible to see the source code. Errors, alerts, features, structural element, HTML5 and ARIA and contrast errors are indicated by different colours.
Full report	Errors and warnings are provided in the line number where they occur (there is a window with the source code where you can check them). The tool provides you a first suggestion to repair the errors/warnings but it's possible to see a full explanation with some example.
Not provided	- Pinpointing of fail/warning in DOM

Figure 22 – WAVE validation form

The screenshot shows the WAVE web accessibility evaluation tool interface. On the left, a sidebar lists the detected issues: 0 Errors, 3 Alerts, 4 Features, 6 Structural Elements, 13 HTML5 and ARIA, and 0 Contrast Errors. The main content area features the title "Web Accessibility Directive Decision Support Environment" and a paragraph explaining the importance of accessibility. A sidebar on the left contains navigation links like "Summary", "Panel Options", "DOCUMENTATION", and "OUTLINE". A code snippet at the bottom shows HTML markup for a menu item with ARIA attributes.

Figure 23 – WAVE report (overview plus contextual graphical details)

1.2.11 Web Accessibility Checker

The Web Accessibility Checker is a tool developed by Mads Kristensen (Microsoft, USA) that can be downloaded as an extension of Visual Studio Code. It uses the Browser Link in the Visual Studio toolbar to test the website running in the browser. The errors found on the running page are reported in the Error List in Visual Studio.

Release date	08/04/2016 (version 1.3) – current version: 1.5
Languages	English, Italian
Guidelines	WCAG 2.0, WCAG 1.0, Section 508, “Other best practices”
License	Free software, Open source
Type of service	Authoring tool: Microsoft Visual Studio
Browser extension	-
Language framework	?
Audit depth	Single web pages, restricted or password protected web pages
Validation source	Running page
Customization of accessibility audits	Provided, by modifying the JSON file that contains all the rules being run.

PRESENTATION OF TEST RESULTS

Report type	Code oriented.
Granularity level of results interpretation	Results are divided into: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Errors • Warnings

<p>Summarizing overview</p>	<p>The report is an Error list with a short description of the problem checked and references to the code lines where they occurred. Double clicking on the single element the user is taken to the location on the source code open in the editing panel.</p>
<p>Full report</p>	<p>The results cannot be filtered by priority level of guidelines. Moreover, guidelines and success criteria regarding the error/warning are not specified. The only filtering possible is by the status of issues.</p> <p>With a right-click on the single element of the Error list, the user can select “Show error help” to receive info regarding errors.</p>
<p>Not provided</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Visualization of fail/warnings on rendered web page - Pinpointing errors/warnings in DOM - Filtering of report by <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o priority level of guidelines o WCAG principle/guideline/success criteria

Figure 24 – Web Accessibility Checker run option

Error List		
Tool	Code	Description
Web Accessibility Checker	audio-caption	<audio> elements must have a captions track
Web Accessibility Checker	video-caption	<video> elements must have captions
Web Accessibility Checker	video-description	<video> elements must have an audio description track
Web Accessibility Checker	color-contrast	Elements must have sufficient color contrast
Web Accessibility Checker	skip-link	The page should have a skip link as its first link

Figure 25 – Web Accessibility Checker report

1.3 Commercial Web Accessibility Services

1.3.1 imergo® Web Compliance Suite

Released initially in 2004 and developed by the Web Compliance Center of the Fraunhofer Institute for Applied Information Technology FIT¹⁵ (Germany), it provides its functionality as a web application and as a REST API for integration in Content Management Systems. The tool is updated and maintained for its provision to different worldwide customers.

imergo® Web Compliance Suite¹⁶ is a complete software suite targeted to improve the quality of web applications by providing a flexible testing framework that can address a wide variety of requirements off-the-shelf, such as mark-up validation and web accessibility. Additionally, it supports the extension of its rule sets through a complete API that allows complex testing of different type of web applications.

The imergo® Web Compliance Suite checks for compliance with international accessibility requirements (Web Content Accessibility Guidelines 2.1). The software has a client/server architecture. The imergo® server contains a crawling service that downloads a set of web pages through a flexible configuration. imergo® evaluates dynamic web pages through its powerful rendering engine, including JavaScript and stylesheets, and can be configured to act as a mobile browser to detect accessibility issues in mobile hybrid applications.

Release date	Since 2004 up to now
Languages	English, German, French
Guidelines	WCAG 2.1, markup validation, customised rules
License	Commercial
Type of service	Web application, REST API
Browser extension	No
Language framework	Complex framework including components in C++, Java and JavaScript (Node.js)
Audit depth	Single web pages, groups of web pages and web sites, restricted or password-protected pages.
Validation source	URL, including full configuration of the HTTP request parameters
Customization of accessibility audits	Through configuration file
PRESENTATION OF TEST RESULTS	
Report type	EARL, HTML

¹⁵ <https://www.fit.fraunhofer.de/>

¹⁶ <https://www.imergo.com/solutions/imergo.html>

Granularity level of results interpretation	Accessibility issues are divided into (based upon EARL ¹⁷): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pass • Fail • Warnings • Cannot tell • Untested • Not applicable
Summarizing overview	yes
Full report	It consists of two views: the error list that can be filtered by types of issue. The error message contains information about the guideline tested, including the corresponding links to techniques, the location of the error in the DOM tree of the page, so that elements can be accessed programmatically and the test result. The reports are created in EARL format. Therefore, it is possible to produce customized reports in any other format e.g. PDF, HTML, Statistical, etc.
Not provided	Visualization of fail/warnings on rendered web page. Although customised visualisers have been created open requests.

1.3.2 Deque systems

Deque Systems is an American digital accessibility company that since 1999 produces accessibility software, in addition to offering accessibility consulting services. Deque tools and services are used to achieve compliance in support of the W3C's Web Content Accessibility Guidelines, the Americans with Disabilities Act and Section 508.¹⁸

1.3.2.1 Amaze

*The target users of this tool are trained **developers** who are **not accessibility experts**. It offers remediation solution for urgent projects and complaint handling that works via the creation of Accessibility Overlays that can correct the issue without having to edit or even access the source code (the accessibility audit is limited to a single web page).*

One of its components is the Amaze Library, which performs the most common accessibility tasks. It includes standards and code best practices that work on multiple browsers/screen-reader/devices. The Developer tools allow developers to implement and test code from within the browser. Accessibility fixes are applied directly in the source code thanks to the Amaze Server.

¹⁷ <https://www.w3.org/TR/EARL10-Guide/>

¹⁸ <https://www.deque.com/products/>

WorldSpace Assure Home Admin Settings Test Cases Test Runs Browser Connection

You are here: Home > Test Runs > Test Run Overview: SmokeTestcase > Checkpoint Tests: Header > 2.4.3.a Focus Order

2.4.3.a Focus Order Component Info < Previous Checkpoint 42 of 66 Next >

Checkpoint Tests Add Issue Flag for Review No Result Pass Fail N/A

All checkpoints Filter

- 1.1 Text Alternatives
- 1.2 Time-based Media
- 1.3 Adaptable
- 1.4 Distinguishable
- 2.1 Keyboard Accessible
- 2.2 Enough Time
- 2.3 Seizures
- 2.4 Navigable
 - Skip Navigation, Headings or Landmarks
 - Titles on Frames
 - Titles on Pages

Focus Order

Overview
The navigation order of links, form elements, etc. must be logical and intuitive.

Testing Methodology

Desktop Web

- Place the cursor in the **URL** field of your browser.
- Press the **Tab** key until focus moves into the page.
- Continue pressing Tab until you reach the end of the document, while ensuring that focus moves from element to element **in a logical and predictable order** and does not jump around erratically.

If focus moves in an illogical order, or jumps around erratically, **fail** this checkpoint. Log an issue for each occurrence.

Mobile Web
Same procedure as Desktop Web.

Native Mobile

Figure 27 – Assure checkpoint explanation

Figure 28 – Assure dashboard

1.3.2.3 WorldSpace Attest

Target users of this automated accessibility testing solution are **component developers, front-end developers and test engineers**, who can catch accessibility errors while coding, with time and cost reduction of manual testing. WorldSpace Attest is based on powerful JavaScript rules libraries and runs on the user's local development server in the same environment as their functional or unit tests. It is fast and easily customizable and integrates with all major testing frameworks. Rules exist for HTML, native Android and native iOS apps.

Attest provides framework integrations (that at the moment include for example Selenium, Cucumber, Qunit) and browser plugins to help users incorporate accessibility into their development and testing environments. In fact, it is thought to be used in the development

phase, when the development team are creating new code and components and can take advantage of Attest for running accessibility tests during their work.

The browser extension is useful for front-end developers to make quick accessibility tests, and it returns detailed information on accessibility violations and how to fix them with a link to more in-depth information. Moreover, Attest can run custom policy settings and custom rules, besides custom integrations with testing frameworks.

Attest provide different reports and in different formats: HTML, JSON, JUnitXML.

Version 1.2.0. Released: 02/12/2016.

Figure 29 – Attest issue description and information

Figure 30 – Assure dashboard

1.3.2.4 WorldSpace Comply

This is an automated testing tool for performing enterprise-level accessibility audits. Its target users are **subject matter experts** and **accessibility managers** of organization with large, dynamic websites. WorldSpace Comply provides advanced scanning, reporting, monitoring (Comply’s reports show accessibility changes over time, at any level of detail), and management of accessibility issues against industry standards or customized guidelines. It provides also support for mobile web browsers by emulating their behaviour. The Dashboard and read-only report provide the list of evaluation results, while the Page section show the accessibility issues within web pages. Step-by-step evaluation guidance is provided.

Figure 31 – Comply dashboard

Figure 32 – Comply dashboard with indications of the code positioning of the issues

1.3.2.5 aXe Chrome and Firefox plugin

aXe is a free, open-source accessibility engine powering several browser extensions and APIs for testing individual web pages for web accessibility errors.

Release date	10/08/2015 (version 1.0.2)
Languages	English
Guidelines	WCAG 2.0, Section 508
License	Open Source
Type of service	Online
Browser extension	Chrome and Firefox
Language framework	JavaScript
Audit depth	Single web pages, groups of web pages or websites, restricted or password-protected pages.
Validation source	The running web page or website.
Customization of accessibility audits	Not provided.
PRESENTATION OF TEST RESULTS (Chrome plugin)	
Report type	The report type is code-oriented and graphical too: the user can choose to see problems highlighted both in the source code and within the analysed web page.
Granularity level of results interpretation	Problems are distinguished in: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Violations • Need review
Summarizing overview	It consists of a list of the violations found, followed by the problems classified as <i>Need review</i> . This list can be filtered by status of issue.
Full report	Clicking on each item of the list, the user can see additional information about the current issue: an issue description, its impact (values are on a scale from minor to critical) the element location (pinpointing of errors/warnings in the DOM is provided), the element source. Moreover, there are links to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Inspect node</i> in the source code • Enable/disable the highlighting the problematic element in the web page • <i>Learn more</i>, that links to the deque University page explaining the violated rule and success criterion, the reason why it is important, and providing the link to the W3C related resource.
Not provided	- Filtering of reports by priority level of guidelines

1.3.3 Siteimprove

1.3.3.1 Siteimprove Intelligence Platform

<https://siteimprove.com/product/content/accessibility/>

Released in 2017, it is a commercial platform. It complies with WCAG 2.0 (Web Content Accessibility Guidelines), Section 508 (US federal procurement standard), JIS (Japanese industry standard), Stanca Act (Italian accessibility legislation) and BITV (German government standard). It supports CSS, HTML, XHTML, PDF documents and images. It checks single web pages, groups of web pages or websites and restricted/password protected pages. There are versions in English, Danish, Dutch, Finnish, French, German, Italian, Japanese, Norwegian, Portuguese, Spanish and Swedish.

It performs entire web site evaluations and provides a bird's eye view of the website's accessibility status. It highlights single page elements such as missing headings and images without alternative text. It provides explanations of issues combined with practical recommendations, and supports handling accessibility issues by distributing prioritized tasks among team members including Web Editors, Developers, and more. It tracks progress toward compliance, providing dynamic progress bars in the Progress section, which monitors improvements over time.

Figure 33 – Siteimprove dashboard

1.3.3.2 Siteimprove Accessibility Checker for Chrome

<https://chrome.google.com/webstore/detail/siteimprove-accessibility/efcfolpjihicnikpmhnmphijhpicllj>

Release date	2017
Languages	English
Guidelines	WCAG 2.0, Section 508, Stanca Act, BITV, JIS
License	Free Software

Type of service	Online
Browser extension	Chrome
Language framework	-
Audit depth	Single web pages, restricted or password protected pages
Validation source	Running web page
Customization of accessibility audits	It is possible to specify the conformance level (A, AA, AAA) for the guidelines, the severity of the reports and the responsibility (it indicates which job role is usually the right one to fix the issue type). You can choose between Editor, Webmaster and Developer role in order to see the results that are more appropriate to be taken into account by the selected role.
PRESENTATION OF TEST RESULTS	
Report type	Statistical
Granularity level of results interpretation	Results are divided into: errors, warnings and review.
Summarizing overview	It's not possible to see the source code because it provides the visualization of the errors/warnings on the rendered web page. The errors/warnings are divided into three categories: error, warning and review.
Full report	The issues are divided into different categories that depend on the error that occurred in the code (for example text alternatives, navigable etc.) It gives users an explanation and a suggestion to repair the error/warning by clicking on the links provided. The errors/warnings don't occur in the line code.
Not provided	- Pinpointing of fail/warning in DOM

Figure 34 – Siteimprove plugin’s customization panel

1.3.4 The Paciello Group (TPG)

1.3.4.1 ARC Monitoring

<https://www.paciellogroup.com/products/arc-monitoring/>

ARC Monitoring is a software developed by The Paciello Group addressed to people interested in monitoring the data that result from scanning their websites to check the compliance against WCAG 2.1, WCAG 2.0 and Section 508, and in tracking progress over time, also by comparing results and trends among different websites and domains. The key features of ARC Monitoring are the Dashboard and the data visualization tools for giving priorities (e.g. success criteria that have higher impact on accessibility) and trends through tables and graphs.

Figure 35 – ARC Monitoring overview

Figure 36 – ARC Monitoring dashboard of a single domain

96.8%**Attributed to Top Three (3) WCAG 2.0 Violations**

Focus on the following success criteria to dramatically improve the accessibility of this page.

5004 [2.4.4 Link Purpose \(In Context\)](#) **Level A**

Principle 2: Operable: User interface components and navigation must be operable.

Guideline 2.4 Navigable - Provide ways to help users navigate, find content, and determine where they are.

919 [4.1.2 Name, Role, Value](#) **Level A**

Principle 4: Robust: Content must be robust enough that it can be interpreted reliably by a wide variety of user agents, including assistive technologies.

Guideline 4.1 Compatible - Maximize compatibility with current and future user agents, including assistive technologies.

265 [1.1.1 Non-text Content](#) **Level A**

Principle 1: Perceivable: Information and user interface components must be presentable to users in ways they can perceive.

Guideline 1.1 Text Alternatives - Provide text alternatives for any non-text content so that it can be changed into other forms people need, such as large print, braille, speech, symbols or simpler language.

Figure 37 – ARC Monitoring list of most problematic checkpoints

Figure 38 – ARC Monitoring performance visualization chart

1.3.4.2 ARC Toolkit

The ARC (Accessibility Resource Center) Toolkit is a testing tool available as a Google Chrome extension, developed by The Paciello Group. It performs quick and efficient evaluations of the accessibility of the running web page against the WCAG 2.1 (the features of Page Reflow and Text Spacing) and WCAG 2.0 level A and AA guidelines, the EN 301 549 and Section 508. The user can access the ARC Toolkit in the Developer Tools, by inspecting the web page and then starting the process of running the test. Additional features are also provided: the user can send the DOM or the URL to an HTML validator

A short video with instructions for use is provided in the ARC Toolkit webpage: <https://youtu.be/FmlzRdLB0mA>.

Link to the ARC Toolkit Quick Start guide: https://www.paciellogroup.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/ARC-Toolkit-Quickstart-Guide-Accessible_Final.pdf

Release date	2017
Languages	English
Guidelines	WCAG 2.1 A and AA
License	Free Software
Type of service	Online
Browser extension	Chrome
Language framework	-
Audit depth	Single web pages, restricted or password protected pages
Validation source	Running web page
Customization of accessibility audits	The test is performed against the default guidelines. The user can select the one or more among the options Hidden issues, Errors, Warnings before starting the test, depending on the type of issues she wants to consider in the evaluation results.
PRESENTATION OF TEST RESULTS	
Report type	Statistical
Granularity level of results interpretation	Results are grouped into: Visible instances, Visible errors, Visible warnings, Hidden instances.
Summarizing overview	In a side column the number of issues are reported in a table, grouped by the result type (Visible instances, Visible errors, Visible warnings, Hidden instances) and by category, called Groups, as well: Media, Structure, Keyboard, ARIA, Color, IDs.
Full report	By clicking on an element of a Group, the user can see the list of the performed test and the Test Results pinpointed in the source-code, accompanied with the name of the test, a brief explanation of the error, and a recommendation useful to fix the problem. In case of warning or error, if the user clicks on the issue, the correspondent HTML element in the web page is highlighted.
Not provided	Pinpointing of errors in the DOM.

The screenshot displays the ARC Toolkit interface within a browser window. The top navigation bar includes 'Elements', 'Console', 'Sources', 'Network', 'Performance', 'Memory', and 'ARC Toolkit'. The main content area is split into three vertical sections:

- Test Groups:** A table summarizing test results across various categories like Page Info, Media, Structure, and Keyboard.
- Visible Assertions:** A table listing specific accessibility tests and their counts of errors and warnings.
- Test Results:** A list of HTML elements with detailed feedback on accessibility issues, such as 'multiple labelling techniques used' and 'placeholder text does not match label text'.

On the right side of the browser window, there is a navigation menu with 'Knowledge centre', 'Events', and 'News'. Below this is an 'ABOUT' section for WADcher and a 'SEARCH' bar with a search input field containing the text '(nesting)'.

Figure 39 – ARC Toolkit panel with the double graphical and code-oriented evaluation results

1.4 Comparison

1.4.1 Validation scope

Among free accessibility assessment tools, Asqatasun, TAW Web, The A11Y Machine, WaaT allow the web designer/developer to evaluate more than a single web page at a time (Total Validator allow to evaluate entire websites only in the Pro version). The considered plugins apply the checking parameters to the single web page that is running in that moment. The validation scope of the commercial services is extended to more than one web page at a time, since they consider entire domains. An extended version of MAUVE that enables the evaluation of multiple pages at the same time is under development.

1.4.2 Customization of the accessibility audit

The customization of accessibility audits is provided by the majority of the free tools: AChecker, Asqatasun, Cynthia Says, imergo, MAUVE, TAW Web, The A11Y Machine, Total Validator, WaaT. However, there are different levels of customization: some of them allow the selection of the preferred guidelines only (among those supported); others also the selection of the priority level of the guidelines.

Figure 40 – Possible customization of accessibility audits feasible with MAUVE (left) and TAW Web (right)

Figure 41 – Screenshot of the evaluation form of the imergo compliance server

The imergo evaluation form in Figure 41 allows a variety of options e.g. selecting different rulesets, only markup validation, only accessibility validation etc.

1.4.3 Validation Overview

As for the presentation of test results, the summarizing overview of the free tools generally provides the total number of issues encountered, divided into the different kinds of problems found during validation (errors, warnings, info/potential problems, ...), and some filtering is possible also at this stage (see examples in Figure 42).

Figure 42 – TAW Web (top) and Asqatasun’s (bottom) summarizing overviews

In regard to commercial services, since they account entire projects, the overview regards the entire evaluated domain, and it is enriched with charts and tables that summarize the accessibility level as well as changes (improvements or worsenings) over time (cfr for example Figure 28, Figure 30 and Figure 35).

1.4.4 Full Report

Concerning the full report, some of the free tools – such as MAUVE., which is code oriented – provide the entire source code with errors and warnings highlighted, and each problem has a link to the W3C guideline explanation.

Figure 43 – M.A.U.V.E. linking from source code to W3C Understanding of the violated guideline

Others, instead, like Tingtun (see Figure 45) provide first a list of problems (that can be filtered by status of issue) with indication of the violated guideline and principle, and then the line code in which the problem occurred; also in this case the tool provides the link to the guideline explanation with examples and tips for the error correction.

The screenshot displays the 'Result Details' interface of the Tingtun tool. It features a 'Applied Tests' section with a list of 17 tests, each showing a status (pass/fail) and a count. The 'Use alt on img elements [1.1.1]' test is highlighted with a red arrow, indicating a failure. To the right, the 'Test Detail' for 'Use alt on img elements (H37)' is shown, including a 'Results' tab with a red 'X' icon and the text 'img has no alt (1 occurrence)'. Below this, a code extract shows the HTML for an image with a missing alt attribute: ``. The 'Test info' tab is also visible.

Applied Tests	Status	Count
Use alt on img elements [1.1.1]	Fail	6, 1
Use of Color [1.4.1]	Pass	86
Provide descriptive titles for web pages [2.4.2]	Pass	1
Provide links to navigate to related Web pages [2.4.5]	Pass	1
Provide descriptive headings [2.4.6]	Pass	9
Primary language of page [3.1.1]	Pass	1
Submit forms without submit buttons [3.2.2]	Fail	1
Provide a submit button to initiate a change of context [3.2.2]	Pass	1
Label groups of form elements [3.3.2]	Pass	1
Define ids for elements [4.1.1]	Pass	116, 1
Accessible name for image links [4.1.2]	Pass	3
Use HTML form controls and links [4.1.2]	Pass	140
Provide role name for div/span with event handler [4.1.2]	Pass	74

Figure 44 – The full report provided by Tingtun

The majority of the tools do not provide the visualization of the errors/warnings on rendered web page, since they are mostly code-oriented. WAVE is the only free tool that provides this kind of report, even if it provides also the pinpointing of problems in the source code. Regarding commercial solutions, Deque's aXe browser extensions allows the developer to highlight issues on the running web page; Siteimprove extension provides this kind of pinpointing too (see Figure 46).

Figure 45 – Pinpointing of WAVE (top), axe for Chrome (middle), Siteimprove (bottom) pinpointing of issues in the rendered web page

The A11Y Machine (Figure 47), Siteimprove Intelligence Platform and WorldSpace Comply provide, in the full report, a dashboard that keeps tracks of the accessibility improvements, allowing the monitoring of the accessibility status over time.

Figure 46 – The A11Y Machine’s Dashboard (<https://github.com/liip/TheA11yMachine>)

1.4.5 Unique features

In regard to other more specific **information provided in the full reports**, The A11Y Machine provides the pinpointing of problems in the DOM, whereas Total Validator, even in the Basic free version, allow the user to check the option “DOM Validation” before starting the evaluation process.

Figure 47 – Full report of the A11Y Machine tool, with pinpointing of problems in the DOM (<https://github.com/liip/TheA11yMachine>)

text: 'Wettersymbole. | Bildquelle: colourbox.com'. Therefore, success criteria 1.1.1 (Non-text Content) and 1.2.1 (Audio-only and Video-only (Prerecorded)) are failed. The alternative to non-text content should serve the equivalent purpose and/or provide equivalent information.

XPath location	Error type
/HTML/BODY/DIV[2]/DIV/DIV[17]/DIV/DIV/DIV[1]/D...	FAIL

Message: The text alternative found cannot be used as an alternative because it is, for example, only a file name or placeholder text: 'Logo der FIFA WM 2018'. Therefore, success criteria 1.1.1 (Non-text Content) and 1.2.1 (Audio-only and Video-only (Prerecorded)) are failed. The alternative to non-text content should serve the equivalent purpose and/or provide equivalent information.

XPath location	Error type
/HTML/BODY/DIV[2]/DIV/DIV[6]/DIV[1]/DIV/DIV/DI...	FAIL

Message: The text alternative found cannot be used as an alternative because it is, for example, only a file name or placeholder text: 'Logo der FIFA WM 2018'. Therefore, success criteria 1.1.1 (Non-text Content) and 1.2.1 (Audio-only and Video-only (Prerecorded)) are failed. The alternative to non-text content should serve the equivalent purpose and/or provide equivalent information.

XPath location	Error type
/HTML/BODY/DIV[2]/DIV/DIV[9]/DIV/DIV/DIV[1]/DI...	FAIL

F38: Failure of Success Criterion 1.1.1 due to not marking up decorative images in HTML in a way that allows assistive technology to ignore them [WCAG 2.0 reference] [4](#)

Message: Check whether this image is used for decorative purposes only. If so, success criterion 1.1.1 (Non-text Content) is failed because an element was found that has an 'alt' attribute that is not null. A null text alternative (i.e., alt="" or role="presentation") needs to be provided to allow assistive technology to ignore decorative images.

XPath location	Error type
/HTML/BODY/DIV[1]/DIV/DIV/DIV[2]/DIV[1]/A/IMG	CANNOTTELL
/HTML/BODY/DIV[1]/DIV/DIV/DIV[2]/DIV[2]/DIV[1]/A/I...	CANNOTTELL
/HTML/BODY/DIV[1]/DIV/DIV/DIV[2]/DIV[2]/FORM/A/IMG	CANNOTTELL
/HTML/BODY/DIV[2]/DIV/DIV[18]/DIV/DIV/DIV[1]/D...	CANNOTTELL

Figure 48 – Screenshot of the imergo HTML report

The imergo report is generated in the EARL format allowing its transformation into many other formats, e.g., PDF or HTML as shown in Figure 48. It contains XPATH addresses of the elements, so programmatic access is easily possible.

As we report in the summarizing tables, all the tools analyzed provide some sort of filtering of the results. Among them, Asqatasun provides the filtering of reports by Web content type, whereas MAUVE groups the detailed results also by the so-called categories (e.g. colors, typography, CSS).

Detailed results Expand all Collapse all

Theme 1 : Images	0	1	5	44	6
Theme 2 : Frames	0	0	0	2	0
Theme 3 : Colours	0	0	3	1	12
Theme 4 : Multimedia	0	0	0	2	28
Theme 5 : Tables	0	0	0	12	0
Theme 6 : Links	1	0	4	11	0
Theme 7 : Scripts	0	0	1	0	12
Theme 8 : Mandatory elements	6	0	3	2	3
Theme 9 : Information structure	2	0	1	0	8
Theme 10 : Presentation of information	2	0	2	2	20
Theme 11 : Forms	0	0	9	14	8
Theme 12 : Navigation	0	0	0	13	13
Theme 13 : Consultation	0	0	6	2	13

Figure 49 – Full report provided by the Asqatasun tool: results are grouped into content types (<https://app.asqatasun.org/home/contract/page-result.html?cr=18&wr=11990>)

Figure 50 – Full report of MAUVE: in the end user view, errors are for example grouped

The commercial services provide new interesting functionalities.

The first one is the fact that some of them – Amaze by Deque, A-Check and A-WEB by Make sense – allow the user to fix the accessibility issues found without accessing the source code of the website/web application.

The second interesting feature offered by Siteimprove – both the Intelligence Platform and the browser extensions – is the possibility to filter the results taking into account the **job role of the user**, that is the most suitable for managing that type of problems (Editor, Webmaster, Developer). Deque Systems, instead, offers different services, each one tailored on the accessibility competence of the user: for example, Amaze is thought for developers who are not accessibility experts, while Comply is addressed to accessibility managers and experts.

Figure 51 – screenshot of Siteimprove Checker for Chrome: the Choose responsibility feature

Previous studies (Paternò and Schiavone, 2015) (Abascal, Arrue, & Valencia, 2019) indicated some issues in the use of automated accessibility tools such as expandability and upgradeability, alignment with the latest technology, and limited effectiveness of the reports. Our analysis confirms such indications and provides an updated state of art.

The table in Appendix: Summarizing table of the analysed tools provides a summary of the features of the analysed tools. We considered both free software and online free services and commercial solutions. The latter are more suitable for evaluating the accessibility of entire projects, that is more than one web page at a time, so complete websites. Free services, in fact, especially if we consider plugins, give an evaluation of a single web page, and do not offer the possibility to see trend over time, except from The A11Y Machine (1.2.6). The monitoring feature is of key importance in our project, since the WAD directive arose the need, especially for web commissioners, to keep track of the accessibility level of the web resources and mobile applications of public sector bodies.

As regards the type of evaluation report that the analyzed tools provide, it emerged that the reports provided are mainly code-oriented. In fact, among the freely available tools, eleven do not provide the visualization of fails and warnings on the rendered web page, a feature that could be useful for not accessibility experts and commissioners, who are not primarily interested into details related to the code.

Other useful features that are not currently supported are related to the filtering of the results. Firstly, in the summarizing overview it is always provided some sort of filtering by status of the issues and by priority level of the guidelines, but the possibility of filtering issues by Web content type is never given to users. This kind of filtering could be provided also in the full report, as Asqatasun does. It would allow web developers and accessibility experts to

better manage their work of fixing errors, by considering problems related to an aspect at a time.

Another feature that is not frequently provided in the detailed reports is the locating of accessibility issues in the DOM, that, on the other hand, is an information that could be useful for accessibility experts and developers.

The last missing feature that we can point out is the possibility to filter the full report by unique or common issues; as for the web content type filtering, it could be useful especially for the accessibility experts' audience.

2 Metrics for Web accessibility

In the domain of web engineering, a metric is a procedure for measuring a property of a web page or website. In the specific context of Web accessibility, metrics measure the accessibility level of websites or indicate large-scale surveys of the accessibility of many websites, being a helpful tool for researchers, developers, governmental agencies and end users.

Accessibility metrics are built on specific qualities of a web page or website. Those qualities can be inherent in a website (e.g. images without the alt attribute), or can be observed from human behaviour, such as user satisfaction ratings or performance indexes like the number of errors.

Properties that can be measured by an accessibility metric could be, for example: the number of pictures without an alt attribute, the number of Level A and Level AA success criteria violations, the number of possible failure points where accessibility problems can occur (e.g. the number of images in a page), the time taken to complete a task, and so on.

The WCAG and other WAI guidelines provide a way to measure the level of accessibility, with the discrete conformance levels “A”, “AA”, and “AAA”. These are an example of **ordinal values**, one of the two types of data that can be produced by the metric’s computation. The other type of data are **quantitative ratio values** (like 0, 15, -15, 0.15).

Depending on the way web accessibility is viewed and defined, two different types of web accessibility metrics can be identified:

- **Conformance-based** metrics, which are based on whether success criteria or given guidelines are met, if we consider accessibility as the conformance of a web page or website to a set of requirements, such as those defined by WCAG 2.0;
- **Accessibility-in-use** metrics, based on performance indexes that can be shown by real users when using the website in specific situations, if we assume that accessibility of a website is a quality that differs from conformance. Section 508, for example, defines accessibility as the extent to which “a technology [...] can be used as *effectively* by people with disabilities as by those without it”. *Effectiveness* is a quality that can be measured, and together with efficiency and satisfaction, that are traditional usability metrics, can be considered as accessibility-in-use metrics.

Existing accessibility metrics are mainly conformance-based, and often provide ratio scores, since ordinal values are less sensitive and precise. They are so widespread because they are based on automated tools, so they are advantageous in terms of time and human resources’ costs; on the other hand, automated conformance-based metrics inherit tool’s shortcomings such as false positives and false negatives, that can affect results, weakening their precision.

2.1 Web Accessibility Metrics Qualities

The increasing number of different released metrics prompted the W3C accessibility working group (Vigo, M., Brajnik, G., & O Connor, J., 2012) to define a framework that encompasses the **qualities that a good metric should have**. The most important factors that can be used to consider if a metric is applicable in a certain scenario, or to characterize the risk inherent in the use of a given metric are:

2.1.1 Validity

It is the extent to which the measurements obtained by a metric reflect the accessibility of the website to which it is applied. Validity depends on the way we intend accessibility:

- Validity with respect to conformance: it reflects how a web document meets specific criteria;
- Validity with respect to accessibility in use: it reflects how the interaction is perceived by real users when interacting with real pages to reach real goals.

It is the most important quality attribute since it tells what a metric really measures.

2.1.2 Reliability

It regards the reproducibility and consistency of scores when evaluations of the same web pages are carried out in different contexts (different tools, guidelines, evaluation processes). Reliability can be meant in two ways:

- Intra-tool reliability: the extent to which scores change depending on the tool's settings (which web pages are analysed and how guidelines are applied);
- Inter-tool reliability: the extent to which reports given by different tools vary when similar settings and same guidelines are applied.

2.1.3 Sensitivity

It is a measure of how changes in metric output are reflected in actual changes to the website. An ideal metric is not much sensitive to small changes in the input content.

2.1.4 Adequacy

It is a general quality that encompasses several properties of accessibility metrics, which determine if they can be suitably deployed in a given scenario. Some of these properties are:

- the type of data used to represent scores;
- precision (the resolution of a scale);
- normalization (in order to make comparisons viable);
- distribution (the span covered by actual values of the metric: if values are distributed on a small interval, large changes in accessibility could lead to small changes in the metric).

2.1.5 Complexity

It reflects how the metric is computationally demanding in terms of time, processors, bandwidth, memory, and in terms of human resources. In fact, some metrics require high bandwidth and large storage capacity to crawl large websites; or, regarding human resources, the complexity may depend on the workflow process needed to resolve conflicts and synthesize a single value. So complexity “reflects the computational and human resources that prevent stakeholders from embracing accessibility metrics”.

This framework has been recently reviewed by (Branjik & Vigo, 2019) in their work on how accessibility metrics have evolved in the last seven years. As regards the qualities of

accessibility metrics, authors underlined that the most important ones continue to be validity and reliability.

A research report on Web accessibility metrics¹⁹ has been drawn up after the Web Accessibility Metric Symposium²⁰, which was held on December 2011, with the main objective of gathering, analysing and discussing practical experiences with measuring website accessibility, including approaches for measuring accessibility in terms of conformance and accessibility-in-use.

A paper presented at the symposium covered the following areas about web accessibility metrics:

- **Validity and reliability:** validity in terms of conformance and inter-tool reliability (Vigo, Abascal, Aizpurua, & Arrue, 2011), and reliability (Fernandes, Lopes, & Carrico, 2011);
- **Tool support for metrics:** from studies presented, it emerged that the public availability of algorithms, APIs and tools is crucial to the wide adoption of accessibility metrics by stakeholders, in particular by those that does not have resources to operate and articulate them.
 - Naftali and Clúa (2011) presented a platform that checks the accessibility of a website according to WCAG checkpoints, where the following accessibility metrics are implemented: Failure-Rate, UWEM score, WAB score. Integrating metrics into the evaluation process proved to be useful as they provide valuable information on the accessibility status of the page, also enabling a quantitative comparison between websites; however, for the most complex checkpoints (usually belonging to AAA level of conformance) human intervention is still required to discard false positives.
 - Fernandes et al.(2011) presented a new feature incorporated into QualWeb (an automatic accessibility evaluator) to detect templates: the metric employed uses the accessibility of the template as a baseline, so that accessibility is measured from that starting point; therefore, the distance from a web page to the baseline is useful to estimate the effort required to fix this instance, which is very valuable for quality assurance.
- **Addressing large-scale measurement:** this issue cannot be faced without the help of automated tools.
 - Fernandes et al. (2011), as seen before, presented a method for template detection that aims at lessening the computing effort of evaluating large amounts of pages, useful in particular for websites that are built on templates, such as online store websites, where the internal structure and layout of pages are mainly the same, whereas the only elements that change are those regarding items on sale.
 - Battistelli et al. (2011) used the **Barriers Impact Factor (BIF)** metric to measure the impact of accessibility barriers in a large number of distinct websites:

¹⁹ Vigo, Brajnik, & O Connor, Research report on Web Accessibility Metrics. W3C WAI Research and Development Working Group (RDWG) Notes, 2012: <https://www.w3.org/WAI/RD/2011/metrics/report.html>

²⁰ Web Accessibility Metric Symposium: <https://www.w3.org/WAI/RD/2011/metrics/Overview.html>

$$BIF_{(i)} = \sum_{error} \#error(i) \times weight(i)$$

- i represents the assistive technologies/disabilities affected by detected errors;
- $error(i)$ represents the number of detected errors which affect i ;
- $weight(i)$ represents the weight that has been assigned to the i assistive technology/disability.

The lowest value of BIF could be 0 and this represents the absence of barriers. The higher is the BIF value, the higher is the impact of a certain barrier on a specific type of assistive technology/disability.

- Nietzio et al. (2011) presented a metric to measure conformance to WCAG 2.0 guidelines in the context of a platform, to keep track of the accessibility of Norwegian municipalities. This metric is an improvement of the UWEM metric, since it considers the checkpoints of WCAG 2.0 (not 1.0 as the latest version).
- Targeting particular accessibility issues: compliance of documents with respect to their DTDs (Battistelli et al., 2011); measurement of text legibility (Rello et al., 2011) Compliance with the DTD and legibility are not only accessibility success criteria, but also quality issues.
- Novel measurement approaches:
 - By considering the distance between a given document and an ideal (or acceptable) one (Battistelli et al., 2011);
 - By considering the distance from an instance document to a baseline template using a metric (Fernandes et al., 2011);
 - By using a five-point Likert scale, to go beyond a binary accessible/not accessible scoring scale (Fischer and Wyatt). The value of their rating levels are: pass (100%), marginally acceptable (75%), partly acceptable (50%), marginally unacceptable (25%), fail (0%);
 - Using “context-tailored” metrics, with a method by which, depending on the context, the number of checkpoints to be met changes (Vigo, 2011); to measure accessibility conformance, it considers not only guidelines, but also the specific feature of the device, as well as the assistive technologies used by the end user;
- Beyond conformance
 - By embracing accessibility in terms of user experience and thinking of conformance of the production process, rather than conformance of a product that constantly changes, as proposed by Sloan and Kelly (2011). In fact, they claim that considering accessibility as conformance to guidelines could be risky in countries where accessibility assessment is focused also in the delivered service and user experience.

Regarding the five quality factors of accessibility metrics (validity, reliability, sensitivity, adequacy and complexity), the authors of this report provided a list of research questions to focus on to ensure metrics’ quality, and proposed some ways to address them. By the way, they agree on the fact that, even all qualities are important, validity and reliability should be given priority: it does not matter how sensitive and adequate a metric is, if its reliability and especially validity are not ensured.

To make metrics more credible and widespread, the authors believe that a good step could be to make a common corpus for metrics benchmarking. Another challenge emerged from the symposium is the personalization of metrics, since not all success criteria impact all users in the same way. Research actions in this direction include the consideration of the users' interaction context in metrics and the weighting of checkpoints according to the impact they have on determined user groups or individual.

2.2 Quantitative metrics for Web accessibility

More generally, quantitative metrics for Web accessibility have been addressed in various scientific contributions. Sullivan and Matson measured accessibility with the “**Failure Rate**” (**FR**), that is the proportion between real and potential failure points on a subset of 8 WCAG 1.0 checkpoints. The result range goes from 0 to 1. FR is good at measuring accessibility as conformance (that requires a FR equal to 0), but other kind of barriers, regarding accessibility in use, may not be reflected on its measurement.

In the context of the KAI – Kit for the Accessibility of the Internet – project (Gonzales, Macias, Rodriguez, & Sanchez, 2003) an accessibility measurement module has been developed, that gives to end-users a global indicator of accessibility at the moment of surfing the net, that could be useful for visually impaired users, especially for blind people. A global accessibility normalized value is computed using the Web Quality Evaluation Method, Web-QEM (Olsina & Rossi, 2002). The KAI makes use of the **Logic Scores Preference (LSP)** method, an aggregation model that calculates a global score from intermediate values obtained as Failure Rate or as absolute number of accessibility issues. This global score is computed as follows:

- Given $E_1...E_n$ a normalized set of scores obtained with the individual metrics, where $0 \leq E_i \leq 1$
- When evaluated components have a different impact, a non-zero convex set for weights $W_1...W_n$ is associated to each single evaluation score, where $0 \leq W_i \leq 1$ and $\sum W_i = 1$.

$$E = \left(W_1 E_1^{p(d)} + \dots + W_i E_i^{p(d)} + W_n E_n^{p(d)} \right)^{1/p(d)}$$

Exponent values are defined elsewhere (Dujmovic, 1997) and are selected on the basis of the fact that the logical relationship necessary between scores is given by fuzzy conjunctions or disjunctions.

Bailey and Burd (Bailey & Burd, 2005) adopted tree maps to see the accessibility level of a website, whose pages are represented by the nodes of the graph. The accessibility metric employed to compute the score is the **OAM (Overall Accessibility Metrics)**, defined as follows:

- $OAM = \sum_c \frac{B_c W_c}{N_{attributes} + N_{elements}}$
 - B_c is the number of violations found for the checkpoint c
 - W_c is the weight of that checkpoint. The weight is calculated in relation to four levels of confidence, depending on how certain is an assessment tool when evaluating a WCAG 1.0 checkpoint.
 - $N_{attributes}$ and $N_{elements}$ are the total number of HTML attributes and elements contained in the web page.

Four level of confidence are defined, depending on how certain is an evaluation tool when evaluating WCAG 1.0 checkpoint (certain: 10, high certainty: 8, low certainty: 4, uncertain: 1).

Later, they (Bailey & Burd, 2007) proposed the **Page Measure (PM)** metric, in order to analyse correlations between the websites' accessibility and the policies adopted by software companies regarding content management systems (CMS) or maintenance strategies. PM is similar to the OAM metric, but in PM the weight corresponds to the **priority** of the checkpoint (priority-1 checkpoints have more impact on the accessibility level of a web page than priority-2 checkpoints, and so on):

$$Page\ Measure = \frac{\sum_c \frac{B_c}{Priority_c}}{N_{attributes} + N_{elements}} \text{ where } Priority_c \in \{1, 2, 3\}$$

Hackett et al. (Hackett, Parmanto, & Zeng, 2004) proposed the **Web Accessibility Barrier (WAB)** metric, that quantitatively measures the accessibility of a website basing on 25 WCAG 1.0 checkpoints. WAB uses as input parameters the total number of pages in the website, the number of potential and real errors in a web page, and error priority: for each page p , the sum of the Failure-Rate of each checkpoint is divided by its priority (that can be 1, 2 or 3); then the score for the entire website is obtained computing the mean over each page's score:

$$WAB = \frac{1}{N_p} \sum_p \sum_c \frac{fr(p,c)}{Priority_c}$$

- N_p is the number of web pages in the website
- $fr(p,c)$ is the Failure Rate of the checkpoint c in page p

This formula does not provide ratings that can be restricted to a range of values: it can be useful only to rank web pages according to their accessibility level.

Sirithumgul et al. (Sirithumgul, Suchato, & Punyabukkana, 2009) proposed the **T¹** metric, that normalizes WAB by applying it to different user groups and selecting WCAG 1.0 checkpoints that have a greater impact on blind and deaf people.

The **Web Accessibility Quantitative Metric (WAQM)** (Vigo, Arrue, Brajnik, Lomuscio, & Abascal, 2007) overcomes some limitations of the previously mentioned metrics. In fact, WAQM provides automatically normalized scores that consider weights of WCAG 1.0 and WCAG 2.0 priorities. Since WAQM is based on reports generated by an automatic software tool (EvalAccess), the checkpoints that can be automatically evaluated have a stronger impact on the final score than the ones that can be evaluated semi-automatically. This metric has been tested in each POUR guideline, and results shown that the Failure-Rate tends to be very low, so that it is difficult to discriminate among different pages since they all get similar accessibility values. So a function is used to distribute such values, in order to assign greater variability scores to low failure rates. This function is an approach to an ideal hyperbole that, the closer to 0 it is the *Error/Tested Cases* ratio (E/T), the higher it will discriminate it: if the FR is

Figure 52 – from Vigo et al. 2007, p. 102

less than the intersection point x' , the accessibility is calculated using the S line; otherwise, the accessibility will be calculated using the V line:

$$x' = \frac{a - 100}{\frac{a}{T} - \frac{100}{b}}$$

$$A = E \times \left(\frac{-100}{b} \right) + 100, \text{ for S line}$$

$$A = \left(\frac{-a}{T} \times E \right) + a, \text{ for V line}$$

Manipulating a and b parameters, it is possible to adapt the WAQM metric to a specific evaluation tool.

During the development process of the **Unified Web Evaluation Methodology (UWEM)** some accessibility metrics have been proposed. In the lastly updated version, UWEM 1.2, the accessibility score of a web page is the mean of the failure rates of all checkpoints (Velleman, Strobbe, Koch, Velasco, & Snaprud, 2007):

$$f(p) = \frac{\sum t B_{pt}}{\sum t N_{pt}}$$

A3 is an extension of the UWEM, and it is defined as follows:

$$A3 = 1 - \prod_p (1 - F_b)^{C_{pb}}$$

- F_b represents the gravity of the barrier b
- C_{pb} is defined as $C_{pb} = \frac{B_{pb}}{N_{pb}} + \frac{B_{pb}}{B_p}$, where B_{pb} and N_{pb} are the total number of real and potential failures of the checkpoint associated to B in the page p, and B_p is the total number of violated checkpoints in the page p.

Lopes and Carriço (Lopes & Carrico, 2008) proposed the **Web Interaction Environments (WIE)** metric. Given the set of checkpoints, V_c is equal to 1 if the checkpoint is reached, otherwise its value is 0. So WIE gives a percentage value of violated checkpoints in the web page (n is the number of checkpoints):

$$WIE(p) = \frac{\sum V_c}{n}$$

The presented accessibility metrics have been classified into two groups by Song et al. (2017), depending on the fact that they consider a weighting factor in the computing of the accessibility score or not. **FR** and **UWEM** are in the group of "Equal metric", because there is not a predefined weight. **WAB** and **WAQM**, instead, are labelled as "Priority metric", because the idea of weighting checkpoints is linked to the priority level indicated by the WCAG for the considered checkpoint.

In their study, Song et al. started from the evidence that the accessibility scores obtained with a "Priority metric" does not reflect the real user experience of people with disabilities, thus arising the need of finding another way of weighting checkpoints, since the priority level is not significantly correlated to the user's ratings of the severity of barriers encountered.

The proposed metric is the **Web Accessibility Experience Metric (WAEM)**, where an optimal weighting is obtained by considering the Partial User Experience Order (PUEXO), that is pairwise comparison between different websites. The representation of the comparison is a pair (a, b) , that represents a comparison between a and b websites made by people with disabilities, where website a has a better browsing experience than website b .

The PUEXO is used to derive the optimal checkpoints weighting with a machine learning model that authors have developed. Given the computed weighting \mathbf{w} , the weighted accessibility score \mathbf{q} of website i can be obtained as

$$q_i = P_i w$$

Where P_i is the vector of all pass rates for website i .

3 Conclusions

The presented analysis has shown the current state of art in terms of automatic tools to support accessibility validation. While many tools have been put forward, there are still a number of limitations of the support that is currently available. The current scenario of the available accessibility tools is rather fragmented, with different tools supporting different set of guidelines, and having limited coverage and accuracy.

The continuous evolution of Web technologies and associated accessibility guidelines requires continuous effort from validation tool developers in order to keep them updated. This is also demonstrated by the limited number of tools supporting the WCAG 2.1 that have recently become a W3C recommendation (5 June 2018, <https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG21/>). WCAG 2.1 was initiated with the goal to improve accessibility guidance for three major groups: users with cognitive or learning disabilities, users with low vision, and users with disabilities on mobile devices. Indeed, in the W3C Web accessibility evaluation tool list²¹, out of the 136 tools listed only 28 of them claim to support WCAG 2.1.

Overall, an integrated, holistic and comprehensive solution to Web accessibility assessment is still missing, which is what we plan to develop in the project in the coming months. In fact, as it emerges from the results given in the comparative table, only commercial services provide monitoring information as feedback, except from some statistical features provided by The Accessibility Machine (see Figure 16 – The A11y Machine Dashboard). One of the effect of the WAD EU directive seems to have stimulated companies interest in accessibility validation because of the potential market possibilities opened up from the monitoring activities required by the directive.

One interesting point is that current accessibility tools provide their users with rather limited opportunities for customization, therefore accessibility tools are not sufficiently flexible in coping with the various needs raised by their users. Moreover, considering the existing accessibility validators, the presentation of the results collected after the accessibility test do not always enable users to fully understand the discovered accessibility problems, so there is the need of advanced solutions able to help accessibility experts to fully understand accessibility barriers more easily and in a more cost-effective manner so as to better act upon them (e.g. fixing them). These are important requirements for the WADcher platform.

It would be desirable that a support environment provides customized presentations of the results, based on the role of the user who is interested in them (Siteimprove Checker provides some support in this direction by providing the possibility to choose among Editor, Webmaster and Developer “Responsibility”). Indeed, there are accessibility-related features in which web developers are more interested in, and others that are more suitable for non-accessibility experts and commissioners.

In the following we indicate the most important features of accessibility assessment tools that emerge from this analysis, according to the type of audience that could most benefit from

²¹ <https://www.w3.org/WAI/ER/tools/>

them. These are features that only a few tools have started to introduce but none of them support all such features.

The presentation of the results addressed to **web commissioners** should provide, at least:

- A summarizing overview with the total number of pass/errors and warnings;
- Possibility of filtering the **summarizing overview** by
 - Status of issues
 - Priority level of guidelines
 - Web content type: this feature is not supported by any tool at the moment.

The presentation of the test results for **web developers and accessibility experts**, instead, should provide:

- The position of errors and warnings in the DOM, a feature that is now supported by The A11y Machine, Total Validator, aXe Chrome and Firefox plugins, Imergo;
- The position of errors and warnings in the source code, with the line number(s) of code related to the detected issue;
- Possibility of filtering the **full report** by
 - Status of issues
 - Highlight most frequent and unique issues: this feature is not supported by any tool at the moment.
 - Priority level of the guidelines
 - WCAG principle/guideline/success criteria
 - Web content type: this feature is supported only by one of the analysed tools (Asqatasun).
- Link to “Understanding” documents.
- Indications of possible suggestions for how to correct the errors.

Finally, it could be useful for **both** categories of users that the reports provide graphical support, locating errors and warnings in the rendered web page, as it is possible when using Wave, aXe Chrome/Firefox plugin and Siteimprove.

The results of this deliverable are thus expected to contribute to complement, validate and further refine the requirements for building a large scale infrastructure in the next coming months in the WADcher project, which integrates automatic web accessibility assessment to better support accessibility expert reviews to detect barriers that could not be detected by current accessibility validators, as well as support developers in understanding and repairing these barriers in a cost-effective manner.

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Appendix: Summarizing table of the analysed tools

Tool	Guideline	Lang.	Validation source	Feedback provided	Validation scope	DOM Check	CSS Check	Plugin	Service
AChecker	WCAG 1.0 WCAG 2.0 Stanca Act Section 508 BITV	Eng Ger Ita	Copied URL; HTML file upload; Pasted HTML code.	Report (code oriented): lines with highlighted and explained errors, warnings, potential problems. Tips for correction provided. Report available in PDF, HTML, CSV, EARL formats.	Single, Restricted or pwd protected web pages	No	yes	No	Online
Asqatasun	WCAG 2.0 RGAA	Eng Fre Spa	Copied URL (or list of URLs); HTML file upload; Scenario upload.	Report: problem list by category (passed, failed, not applicable, pre-qualified, not tested). Details and tips for correction provided. Report available in PDF, ODS, CSV formats.	Single, Groups of web pages or web sites, Restricted or pwd protected web pages	No	yes	No	Online
MAUVE	WCAG 2.1 WCAG 2.0 Stanca Act Visually impaired	Eng	Copied URL; HTML file upload; Pasted HTML code.	Report (code oriented): lines with highlighted and explained errors/warnings. Links to w3c correction techniques provided for each problem.	Single web pages	No	Yes	Chrome Firefox	Online
WAVE	WCAG 2.0 Section 508	Eng	Copied URL	Report: summary of problems. In-page feedback: rendered page with indicated problematic elements; explanation of problems provided.	Single, Groups of web pages or web sites, Restricted or pwd protected web pages	No	Yes	Chrome Firefox	Online

Tool	Guideline	Lang.	Validation source	Feedback provided	Validation scope	DOM Check	CSS Check	Plugin	Service
Cynthia Says	WCAG 2.0 Section 508	Eng	Copied URL	Report: problems grouped by compliance level and violated criteria. Explanation provided. Printable version of report available.	Single web pages	No	Yes	No	Online
WAAT	WCAG 2.0 WCAG 1.0 WAI-ARIA 1.0	Eng	Copied url (choice: one page, n° of pages of the entire website); Pasted source code.	Report (code oriented, statistical): errors and warnings list by violated principle; code line and tips for the correction provided. Report available in PDF and EARL formats.	Single, Groups of web pages or web sites	No	Yes	No	Online, Desktop application
Web Accessibility Checker	WCAG 2.0 WCAG 1.0	Eng	Running webpage	Report: explained error/warning list. Step-by-step evaluation guidance: additional help provided for each error.	Single, Restricted or pwd protected web pages	No	Yes	No	Online, Authoring tool: Microsoft Visual Studio
The A11Y Machine	WCAG 2.0 WCAG 1.0 Section 508	Eng	Copied URL (or list of URLs)	Report (code oriented, statistical): index of all reports, report of a specific URL, dashboard of all reports. Report available in CLI, CSV, HTML (default), JSON or markdown formats.	Single, Groups of web pages or web sites, Restricted or pwd protected web pages	No	Yes	No	npm installation
Total Validator	WCAG 2.0 WCAG 1.0 Section 508	Eng	Copied URL (additional: pages to check NOT available in the free version)	Report (code oriented): lines with highlighted and explained errors/warnings.	Single, Groups of web pages or web sites, Restricted or pwd protected web pages	No	Yes	Chrome Firefox	Desktop application
TAW Web	WCAG 2.1 WCAG 2.0	Eng Spa Por	Copied URL	Report (statistical): n° of errors/warnings by violated principle. Detailed report sent via email.	Single web pages, web sites	No	Yes	No	Online, Desktop application

Tool	Guideline	Lang.	Validation source	Feedback provided	Validation scope	DOM Check	CSS Check	Plugin	Service
EIII/Tingtun	WCAG 2.0	Eng Nor	Copied URL	Report (code oriented, statistical): n° of error/warning and global score (0 to 100). Result details, divided by criteria, show code lines, description of the error and tips for correction.	Single web pages	No	Yes	No	Online
Imergo	WCAG 2.0 Section 508 BITV	Eng Ger Spa	Copied URL (additional: number of pages to check)	Report (code oriented): index of reports, sortable list of errors, warnings and info by Rule Set; xpath to code lines and explanation message provided for each problem. Links to WCAG 2.0 techniques for correction tips.	Single web pages, group of web pages, websites; Restricted or pwd protected web pages	Yes	Yes	No	REST API for CMS integration Desktop Application
Siteimprove Intelligence Platform	WCAG 2.0 Section 508 JIS Stanca Act BITV	Dan Dut Eng Fin Fre Ger Ita Jap Nor Pot Spa Swe	Copied URL	Report (code oriented): n° of error/warning and global accessibility score (0 to 100). The detailed report provides explanation of issues, tips for correction (specific for the team's members), highlighting of elements in the page. The Progress section keeps track of improvements over time.	Single web pages, Groups of web pages or websites and Restricted or pwd protected pages	Yes	Yes	Chrome	Online (hosted service)
Deque Systems Amaze	WCAG 2.0 Section 508	Eng	Running web page	Accessibility fixes are applied directly in the source code.	Single web pages	No	Yes	No	Hosted Service
Deque Systems WorldSpace Assure	WCAG 2.0 Section 508	Eng	Copied URL	Report: detailed list of issues for developers, with step-by-step guidance. Comprehensive report showing common defect types and trends over time.	Groups of web pages or websites, Restricted or pwd protected web pages	No	Yes	Chrome Firefox Internet Explorer	Hosted Service

Tool	Guideline	Lang.	Validation source	Feedback provided	Validation scope	DOM Check	CSS Check	Plugin	Service
Deque Systems WorldSpace Attest	WCAG 2.0 Section 508	Eng	Copied URL	Report: detailed list of accessibility violations and how to fix them (step-by-step guidance). Links to more in-depth information are provided.	Groups of web pages or web sites, Restricted or pwd protected web pages	Yes	Yes	Chrome Firefox Internet Explorer ≤ 8	Hosted Service
Deque Systems WorldSpace Comply	WCAG 2.0 Section 508	Eng	Copied URL	Dashboard and read-only report; section Page displaying information within web pages; step-by-step evaluation guidance provided. Tracking of accessibility changes over time provided.	Groups of web pages or web sites, Restricted or pwd protected web pages	No	Yes	No	Hosted Service
Make sense A-Check	WCAG 2.0, 2.1 AA Section 508 ADA (American with Disabilities Act) EN 301549	Eng Additional languages per request	Copied URL	Report includes n° of issues, the specific rule violation, the location of the issues; for each error a suggestion of the correct code line is provided; step-by-step instructions to assist in manual fixing are provided.	Groups of web pages or web sites, Restricted or pwd protected web pages	No	?	No	Hosted Service
Make sense A-WEB			Loaded website	The script installed on the website automatically transforms it to meet all required accessibility standards (sometimes manual adjustments must be made).	Groups of web pages or web sites, Restricted or pwd protected web pages	No	?	No	Cloud service.
Make sense A-ToGo			Running website	End users can make accessibility adjustments directly on the webpage they are visiting.	Groups of web pages or web sites, Restricted or pwd protected web pages	No	?	Chrome	Online

Tool	Guideline	Lang.	Validation source	Feedback provided	Validation scope	DOM Check	CSS Check	Plugin	Service
ARC Toolkit	WCAG 2.1 (some features) WCAG 2.0 EN301549 Section 508	Eng	Running web page	Report (graphical, statistical, code oriented): total n° of issues are grouped by the result type (Visible instances, Visible errors, Visible warnings, Hidden instances) and by Groups well (Media, Structure, Keyboard, ARIA, Color, IDs). Issues are explained and pinpointed in the html code, and the corresponded element in the rendered web page is highlighted	Single web page	No	Yes	Chrome	Online
ARC Monitoring	WCAG 2.1 (some features) WCAG 2.0 EN301549 Section 508	Eng	Copied URL	Report (graphical, statistical): it provides charts and tables to show the accessibility level and to track its trends over time	Groups of web pages or web sites, Restricted or pwd protected web pages	No	Yes	No	Online (hosted service)

Table 1 – Summary of the analysed tools.

